

Analyzing leaf number in parental lines for hybrid rice seed production

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Determining the seeding interval between two parents in any hybrid combination at a given location is of prime importance for achieving perfect synchronization in a hybrid rice seed production plot. Fixed growth duration, commonly practiced in India, is a simple and easy method to adopt. But fluctuations in temperature and other weather conditions influence maturity. Leaf number, unlike growth duration of a rice variety, is reported to be relatively stable over seasons and years.

We studied leaf number and growth duration in promising parental lines

and their utility in hybrid rice seed production. The experimental material included male sterile lines (IR58025A and IR62829A), restorer lines (IR10198R, IR40750R, IR54742R, and IR29723R), and inbred variety Vajram. They were grown in the field in the 1994-95 wet season (WS) and dry season (DS). A three-division method of counting leaves was adopted; the values for developing leaves are given as 0.2, 0.5, and 0.8 for just-emerged, half-emerged, and almost-opened leaf, respectively, keeping the fully opened previous leaf as a reference. Besides growth duration, observations were recorded on leaf number by using 12 competitive plants in each entry and counting leaves at an interval of 5 d from the 3rd leaf stage until the flag leaf stage.

Results revealed that growth duration fluctuated and depended on season and year. This fluctuation was less (3-14 d) in cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) and restorer lines of medium

duration—IR58025A, IR62829A, IR10198R, and IR40750R—compared with late-maturing restorers (3-29 d). The leaf number of a variety or A and B lines did not vary over seasons or years. The rate of leaf emergence depended on season and stage of plant growth. Leaf emergence is faster in the WS (5 d to emerge) than in the DS (7-8 d). During the growth period, the rate of leaf emergence declined after 65 and 75 d after sowing in the WS and DS, respectively. In general, early-duration varieties showed a lower number of leaves than late-maturing varieties.

We have not found any appreciable difference among CMS lines and early and late restorers for their rate of leaf emergence. Based on this study, we suggest adopting 3-4 staggered sowing of parental lines at an interval of 5 d so that leaf number index can be used as an aid in hybrid rice seed production. ■

Identifying some favorable environments for hybrid rice seed production in Andhra Pradesh, India

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Outcrossing in rice mainly depends on climatic factors. Favorable environments increase hybrid seed production. Likewise, synchrony in flowering of male and female parents also increases seed set. We therefore conducted two trials to investigate these two important aspects. A trial was conducted in semiarid and humid zones of Andhra Pradesh during the 1991-92 wet season (WS) and dry season (DS), using IR62829A and IR62829B in a row ratio of 4A:2B. Sowings of A and B lines were staggered. Leaf clipping and rope pulling were adopted. The outcrossing percentage was higher at Palem and Warangal, located in the semiarid zone (>40%), than at Maruteru, located in the

humid zone (<20%) in both seasons. Seed yield was also higher in the semi-arid regions in the 1991 WS (Palem, 959 kg ha⁻¹; Warangal, 1,191 kg ha⁻¹) and 1992 DS (Palem, 1,527 kg ha⁻¹) than in the humid zone (Maruteru, WS 408 kg ha⁻¹ and DS 851 kg ha⁻¹).

To achieve flowering synchronization in the seed production plots, precise information on the phenological behavior of the parental lines is essential in the target environments. With this objective, a second trial was conducted during the 1995 WS at seven locations representing four different agroclimatic zones in Andhra Pradesh. The material for this study included parental lines (A and R lines) of released and prerelease hybrids. In different agroclimatic zones, from location to location, in all three CMS lines and five restorer lines, flowering duration varied: 81-105 d in IR58025A, 77-105 d in IR62829A, and 90-155 d in PMS 3A. A similar trend was also observed in the restorer lines. The differences in flowering duration in each R line varied from 26 to 34 d in different agroclimatic zones. ■

Seasonal influence of flowering behavior and plant growth characters on parental lines of hybrid rice

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Parental lines of hybrid rice—A lines (IR62829A and IR58025A), B lines (IR62829B and IR58025B), and R lines (IR10198-66-2R, AS 89044, and Pusa 150R)—were raised at monthly intervals from August 1994 to July 1995. The recommended cultivation practices were adopted and observations were made in 10 randomly selected plants from each population. During the cropping period, data on maximum and minimum temperature and hours of sunshine and daylength were obtained from agrometeorological documentation records. From this, heat unit concepts—growing degree days (GDD), relative temperature disparity